

OUTLOOK

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Quantifying the Mutual Requirements
Driving AI and 6G Co-Evolution

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White Paper
Quantifying the Mutual Requirements Driving AI and 6G Co-Evolution

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1. Introduction

The co-evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) and sixth-generation cellular network (6G) constitutes a foundational phase in the digital infrastructure, in which we are witnessing an era where connectivity and intelligence are converging at the system, architectural, and operational levels. Unlike previous wireless generations, where AI was an add-on applied post-deployment to optimize particular isolated functions, 6G is being designed as AI-native from the ground up, embedding AI into the core architecture, interfaces, and service models. While AI is expected to play a central role in enhancing the design, deployment, and operation of 6G networks, the opposite is equally important, in the sense that 6G should be purposely designed to support the stringent requirements of advanced AI workloads, including among others, federated learning, generative AI (GenAI) applications, etc.

A recent industry report shows that Telcos anticipate over 20% gains in revenue or cost efficiency through AI adoption, particularly in domains such as network operations, customer service, and software development [1]. AI use cases such as network capacity planning, field service assistance, and automated code generation, to name a few, are already making a notable impact in the telecom sector. However, the deployment of AI at scale introduces new pressures on the network itself, requiring 6G systems to evolve to meet new expectations of ultra-low latency, distributed intelligence, dynamic resource allocation, and energy-efficient operation [2].

This two-way relationship, AI for Network and Network for AI, requires a fundamental shift in network design. To illustrate, while AI can be utilized to optimize handovers, network behaviour, resource allocation, etc., the network itself must enable programmable interfaces, reliable compute nodes, and data processing pipelines that enable distributed AI training and inference. Emerging concepts such as AI-as-a-Service and LLM-driven orchestration further demonstrate how 6G will not only serve as an AI-optimized communication fabric but as a native computational platform for serving AI workflows [3].

The aim of this white paper is to characterize, in a quantitative manner, the two-way relationship between AI and 6G, AI for Network and Network for AI, by identifying the infrastructure and system demands that advanced AI workloads, such as large language models (LLMs), GenAI, and distributed learning, impose on 6G networks. In parallel, we will articulate the enabling capabilities that 6G must deliver to effectively support, accelerate, and scale the deployment of AI across diverse use cases. This entails examining performance requirements such as latency, bandwidth, energy efficiency, and data accessibility, which are essential for realizing the full potential of AI-driven services in next-generation networks.

2. Measuring the Impact of AI in 6G

Although the long-term impact of GenAI models on telecom networks remains difficult to quantify, several recent studies have outlined the most promising expected use cases [4]. A recent survey, based on data from 104 senior-level respondents from 73 communication service providers (CSPs), has identified seven distinct families of use cases which are either being explored already today, or have short- to mid-term potential [5]: Customer operations, marketing and sales, network, information technology (IT), and software engineering, product innovation, internal knowledge, and business operations (see Table 2-1).

Table 2-1 Families of GenAI use cases for mobile network operators (MNOs) [5].

Family	Use Cases
Customer operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer chatbot. - Call center agent documentation and coaching. - Website assistance. - Predictive and personalized services.
Sales & marketing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marketing collateral generation. - Personalized customer/email scripts. - Social media automated responses.
Network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Field service operations guided assistance. - Network/capacity planning. - Network security testing. - Post-mortem creation. - Root cause analysis.
IT / software engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automated code generation and testing. - Automating repetitive tasks. - Detection of code security vulnerability.
Product innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carrier billing. - Personalized services. - Voice value-added services. - business-to-business (B2B) customer call services.
Internal knowledge, training & development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluating new trends/developments. - Competitive analysis. - Supply chain analysis.
Business operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contract. - Fraud management. - Partner management. - Human resources.

More recently, an analysis has been published presenting how GenAI models could help telcos to improve their revenues, based on a response from 130 telco operators in North America, Latin America, Europe, Africa, Asia, and the Middle East [1]. This document has identified five families of use cases: customer service, marketing and sales, network, IT and support functions.

Further details related specifically to network use cases include:

- Network planning: GenAI models facilitate planning by optimizing coverage, capacity, and bandwidth, and provide enhanced tools to improve the efficiency of network design [6].

- Network deployment: These models can be used for network deployment to reduce the launch time for new telecom services or network features, including configuration, testing, and tuning phases [6].
- Network management and orchestration: GenAI aids network management by diagnosing issues and providing solutions to optimize resource, function, and service orchestration, particularly beneficial in integrating network and computational resources, thus improving network reliability and stability [7].

2.1. Business value of the use cases

Table 2-2 describes the anticipated impact of GenAI models across different business domains [1]. This table highlights that over 85 percent of executives expect GenAI to deliver more than 20 percent in revenue gains or cost savings across various business domains. Notably, customer service along with marketing and sales represent the largest expected share of this impact in terms of business value. For example, AI chatbots are projected to enhance efficiency in customer support, potentially reducing related costs by 15 to 20 percent. Moreover, GenAI models employed to summarize voice and written client interactions could reduce associated costs by as much as 80 percent.

Table 2-2 GenAI models impact on telcos by use cases [1].

Business Domain	Share of Total Impact (%)	Share of Surveyed Business Leaders Focused on Domain (%)	Example Use Cases
Customer Service	35	85	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Customer-facing chatbots - Call-routing performance - Agent copilots - Bespoke invoice creation
Marketing and Sales	35	45	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content generation - Hyper-personalization - Copilots for store personnel - Customer sentiment analysis and synthesis
Network	15	62	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Network inventory mapping. - Network optimization via customer sentiment analysis. - Self-healing via customer sentiment analysis on network problems.
IT	10	55	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copilots for software development. - Synthetic data generation. - Code migration. - IT support chatbots.
Support Functions	5	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Procurement optimization. - Workplace productivity. - Internal knowledge management. - Content generation HR Q&A.

In marketing and sales, MNOs can leverage GenAI models to create personalized messages and visual media tailored to individual customers. For instance, a European MNO reported achieving over a 10 percent customer conversion rate in a recent pilot project using this approach. Within network-related use cases, GenAI models enhance network planning and management capabilities by analysing and structuring data about network components, including specifications and supplier maintenance information. Similarly, within IT domains, software developers can complete coding tasks up to twice as fast with GenAI models [8]. Furthermore, GenAI applications in support functions have shown the potential to significantly reduce back-office operational costs while simultaneously increasing employee productivity, the same MNO anticipates a 30 percent improvement in productivity due to GenAI adoption. Such trends align closely with findings from a recent survey of more than 400 telecom professionals [9], which highlighted that among those investing in AI, 57 percent apply GenAI to customer service, 57 percent to employee productivity enhancements, 48 percent to network operations and management, 40 percent to network planning and design, and 32 percent to marketing content generation.

2.2. AI Training as a Service in 6G Networks

In future telecommunication networks, data will be generated from various sources and collected by sensors, cameras, radars and lidars on multiple terminals. At the same time, with the rapid development of high-end terminals, exploiting distributed on-device processing capabilities opens the door for new AI added-value services. In this use case, 6G networks can provide the AI Training as a service in a collaborative and efficient manner by connecting data silos to enable powerful AI model production. In our vision, AI training as a service encompasses two main categories: AI for Network and Network for AI. In AI for Network, an AI/ML model supports the network functions of the network. Conversely, in Network for AI, the network monetizes available resources and capabilities, such as data collection and storage, to offer AI training services to consumers through dedicated interfaces.

Fig. 2-1 illustrates a high-level description of the AI training as a service use case. Collected data can be transferred to the network side, where datasets are built up and used to generate powerful AI models in a centralized way. An alternative is training AI models locally instead of uploading the local raw data to the central processing centre. Choosing between centralized and distributed AI model training approaches depends on several considerations [10] [11]. First, the decision considers the processing capabilities of the involved training entities. Second, the privacy protection of the local data should be ensured. Finally, the resources for training the AI model should be optimized.

Considering current network technologies, the successful deployment of the AI training as a service use case requires to fulfil the following gaps:

- Current telecommunication networks primarily support AI for Network training (e.g., estimating or forecasting quality of experience (QoE), network load) but provide limited support for Network for AI training, typically available only at the user equipment (UE) and application layers.
- If 6G networks offer AI Training as a Service, there will be a need to jointly consider AI training-related requirements alongside traditional network services (such as connectivity) and optimize resource allocation accordingly.

Figure 2-1 AI Training as a Service.

2.3. AI Inference as a Service in 6G Networks

The rapid adoption of AI throughout society has facilitated the development of numerous new applications across various sectors, including individual users, industry, and public organizations. According to our vision, 6G networks, empowered by intelligent decision-making capabilities, will become critical platforms for delivering AI-based services. In this use case, the networks can provide AI inference as a service in a collaborative and efficient manner. Like AI training as a service, AI inference as a service comprises two main families of use cases: AI for Network and Network for AI.

Fig. 2-2 illustrates three distinct examples of AI inference as a service provided by a 6G network:

- Fig. 2-2(a) shows the case where the network handles the whole AI inference workload. In this case, user data might require preprocessing to facilitate efficient transmission (e.g., to reduce overhead and latency) and to address privacy and security concerns related to data sharing. AI model inference could be split across various network nodes to leverage different resource availabilities or proximity to users. However, splitting AI inference across multiple nodes introduces challenges related to synchronization, security, communication overhead, and latency.
- Fig. 2-2(b) presents a scenario in which AI inference is distributed into multiple inference tasks performed by the network and external entities (e.g., users, devices, applications, and interconnected networks). Inferring part of the AI model at the UE side reduces the communication requirements of the AI/ML model inference and enhances the privacy protection, as only the output of the locally processed model (i.e., extracted data features) is transmitted to the network side.
- Fig. 2-2(c) illustrates yet another possibility of offloading the AI/ML model inference to the network. In this example, an AI-enabled application requires data from multiple

sources and may deliver its results to multiple consumers. The AI/ML model inference is supported by different AI-Agents in the network charged of specific processing for the AI-enabled application (e.g., multi-stream, multi-modal fusion applications). The control and fulfilment of the system requirements formed by the data sources, AI-Agents, network nodes, and consumers of the application are performed intelligently by the network.

Fig. 2-2 represents the case where data, resources, and models are controlled by telecom network operators, applicable for both AI for Network and Network for AI cases. Additionally, other variants are possible, such as the cases where: 1) The application owns both the AI model and data, leasing only the necessary network resources from the operator for AI inference; 2) The application owns the data and leases from the operator the necessary resources for the AI inference process including the AI model; 3) The application leases from the operator the necessary resources for the AI inference process including the AI model taking as input network data.

Figure 2-2 AI Inference as a Service.

2.4. LLMs in 6G networks

LLMs are AI models with the ability to process information and demonstrate human-like text generation capabilities. In the context of 6G networks, LLMs have three main general capabilities that can be used to offer new value-added services [12]:

- Semantic capabilities: LLMs develop an internal representation of textual data in the form of real-valued vectors called embeddings. LLMs can process and comprehend intricate information, such as the content within standard documents and infer logical conclusions from the given inputs.
- Intelligent Access to Knowledge: by understanding the specific intention conveyed through the prompt, an LLM can effectively apply its knowledge base to craft a response tailored to the user needs.
- LLMs as Orchestrators: LLMs can utilize their knowledge to deconstruct complex tasks into manageable subtasks and deploy suitable (external) tools for each (see Figure 2-3).

Given these capabilities, integrating LLMs into 6G networks becomes critical in two distinct contexts:

- AI for Network: LLMs can leverage the large amount of textual data, such as network anomalies tickets, product manuals, and software to support the end-to-end network lifecycle, including requirement understanding, planning, design and simulation, implementation, tuning, evaluation and optimization (see Fig. 2-4).
- Network for AI: 6G networks can leverage communication resources to support coordination between LLM based AI agents, LLM transfer and distributed training. In addition, the AI-native telecommunication network can provide data collection capabilities and resources for LLM training and assessment.

Figure 2-3 LLM based intent-driven network [13].

In the context of 6G networks, an AI agent is an entity capable of interacting with the network environment and that uses AI task-specific capabilities for achieving the goals of the 6G network and its environment. Interactions may include, but are not limited to, data collection, usage of tools (e.g., search engines, databases, devices, other AI agents external to the network) through related Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and sharing agent-generated outputs with the 6G network and its environment through a dedicated interface.

Figure 2-4 AI agents for network policy evaluation.

3. 6G Functional Requirements Shaped by AI

The next generation of AI, especially artificial general intelligence (AGI), is expected to play a significant role in the design, development, and operation of 6G technologies [14]. In contrast to previous generations of wireless systems, where AI was typically integrated post-deployment primarily as a tool to enhance specific functions (e.g., traffic prediction and resource allocation) [15], 6G is conceived as a fundamentally AI-native infrastructure. In this new paradigm, telecom networks will leverage AI for interacting with its environment, enabling novel value-added services, and enhancing the performance of network and services. To realize this vision, the 6G network will host new functions and interfaces to fully support the machine learning (ML) model lifecycle as well as the joint optimization of connection, data collection and processing, algorithms, and models in the AI-native telecommunication network and its environment.

3.1. Data management

The 6G network will natively support data lifecycle management of the entire data process for AI training and inference including data collection, transmission, processing, storage, and consumption:

- 6G network should support data collection with different time granularities in terms of resources, networks and services.
- 6G network should support data processing for AI, including data processing to enhance data format, quality, privacy, and security.
- 6G network should support data management for supporting AI Training, Testing, and Validation.
- 6G network should create and maintain knowledge base for supporting Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) [16].
- Data management functions for obtaining, storing and processing private user data must be defined in accordance with enforced regulations [4].
- 6G network may use both user data and network-controlled information to support AI/ML new value-added services.

3.2. Resource & QoS Monitoring

According to Lord Kelvin statement, “If you can’t measure it, you can’t improve it”, continuous resource and quality of service (QoS) measurements are the basis in 6G networks for successful and cost-effective AI service provisioning. Importantly, the following functions and interfaces should be introduced or enhanced:

- Functions for monitoring the status of AI resource usage.

- Function for monitoring the AI service performance requirements, such as AI model accuracy, AI service latency, or AI service density.¹

3.3. 6G Interfaces for LLMs and AI agents

To take full advantage of the LLMs capabilities (semantic and orchestration capabilities, as well as access to knowledge) as described in Section 2.4, 6G networks shall support the following interfaces:

- Interface to expose LLMs to the available knowledge base.
- Interface to expose LLMs to the business intents.
- Interface to expose LLMs to network operator policies.
- Interface to expose LLMs to network resource availabilities, user QoS and network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- Interface to enable coordination among AI agents.
- Interface to enable AI agents' usage of tools such as search engines, databases, and devices.

3.4. Resource Optimization

6G networks need to jointly consider the requirements of AI value-added services together with the requirements of other (e.g., connectivity) offered services and optimize resource allocation accordingly. To achieve this goal, 6G networks integrate mechanisms and support functions for:

- Prioritizing requirements between AI Training services and other services offered by the network, considering jointly communication and AI resources.
- Benchmarking available AI models with respect to a target AI service, for example, by generating and running tests to assess the service required capabilities.²
- Determining the AI model and its configuration for a requested service offered by the 6G network. This task shall take into consideration the status of communication and AI resources.

3.5. Resource-aware model training and inference

AI consumes a notable amount of resources, including data and compute. In addition, AI/ML applications usually leverage different AI/ML models perform the same task under different conditions with the intention to select the most accurate result [17].

¹ i.e., the number of AI models running in a given area.

² AI capabilities may include, but are not limited to, decision-making, reasoning, forecasting, clustering, classification, self-learning, acquiring contextual information, natural language processing, and complex tasks decomposition.

6G should integrate in a native manner the capability to adapt AI models and the entire model lifecycle, including data collection and model download, to time-space varying available network resources. To attain this objective, the following mechanisms and related functions are expected:

- Intelligent mechanism for dynamically split the AI training and inference workload between the 6G network and its environment, based on resource availabilities.
- Intelligent AI training mechanism that constructs AI models able to work in different configuration (see Fig. 3-1) to trade-off AI service performance with network resource usage [18].
- Intelligent mechanism to transfer additional layers of AI models to the inference endpoint to increase the model performance upon changes on the network conditions and AI service requirements [18].

Figure 3-1 Illustration of a flexible AI training [18].

4. 6G Performance Requirements Shaped by AI

6G systems will provide new added-value services integrating AI and leveraging telecommunication network communication and computing capabilities. Specifically, AI for Network refers to services that optimize the telecom network performance by employing AI/ML on network-specified functionalities and capabilities. This shift represents an incremental improvement in network planning strategies and a transformative advancement, providing 6G networks with real-time, autonomous decision-making, self-healing, and ubiquitous human-machine interactions. In addition, Network for AI refers to services that provide network support for AI/ML-based applications and services, such as training and inference.

These new added value services based on AI necessitate 6G networks to handle significant amounts of real-time data and adapt to changing conditions. For example, 6G systems must meet extreme performance requirements, including scalable and decentralized computing resources for AI workloads, energy-efficient technologies to temper resource consumption for computation-intensive processing, and more dependable or resilient self-healing fast-fail mechanisms [2]. Table 4-1 outlines the critical requirements that 6G must satisfy to effectively support AI-driven applications. These include ultra-low latency to facilitate real-time AI applications like autonomous vehicles and augmented reality (AR) surgery, energy-efficient data pipelines essential for sustainably deploying large-scale AI workloads, high-bandwidth provisions for ultra-HD applications and sensor data fusion, distributed AI architectures that enable scalable, privacy-preserving operations, and robust security and privacy protocols to protect sensitive data. Additionally, ethical and regulatory compliance frameworks are highlighted as essential for ensuring transparency, accountability, and equitable decision-making within autonomous AI-driven processes. The following subsections provide detailed explorations of these key AI-shaped requirements and their respective roles in shaping the future of 6G infrastructure.

4.1. Ultra-Low Latency

Ultra-low latency (less than 1 millisecond) is a major requirement for AI applications that demand instant decision making, such as coordinating autonomous vehicles, performing real-time AR surgery, and completing in-flight predictive maintenance for aviation systems [19]. To achieve this ultra-low latency, 6G systems need specialized hardware capable of fast AI processing directly at the network edges. For instance, embedding neural processing units (NPUs), which are a type of processors optimized explicitly for handling AI tasks quickly and efficiently, in 6G base stations (BSs). Consequently, AI processing occurs closer to the users and devices, significantly reducing delay. Moreover, strict QoS policies must be established specifically for these critical AI services. To enforce QoS policies, deterministic network protocols, such as IEEE 802.1 time-sensitive networking (TSN) [20], can be employed to ensure predictable and reliable latency even in heterogeneous networks with many connected devices.

Unlike the previous generation of wireless systems, 6G networks will proactively manage latency-sensitive tasks by employing AI-based prediction methods. These methods predict traffic patterns and allocate resources ahead of demand, thus further reducing potential delays. Moreover, using edge computing and intelligent network orchestration can limit unnecessary long-distance data transfers (backhaul). Finally, adopting new wireless

waveforms and ultra-wide frequency bands will make signal delays negligible. Meeting these ultra-low latency demands ensures 6G will support current AI applications and enable future AI scenarios with even stricter real-time requirements.

Table 4-1 Key Performance Requirements for 6G Networks to Support AI.

Performance Requirements	Key Challenges & Drivers	AI-Driven Solutions & Technologies	Applications & Implications
Ultra-Low Latency	Real-time AI applications (e.g., autonomous vehicles, AR surgery) require < 1 ms latency.	- Edge AI with NPUs for local processing. - TSN protocols for deterministic latency. - AI traffic prediction and THz waveforms.	Enables mission-critical AI tasks (e.g., remote surgery, autonomous systems).
Resource-Efficiency	High resource demands of AI workloads (e.g., LLMs, GenAI).	- Neuromorphic computing (SNNs). - Model quantization/pruning. - Solar-powered nodes and resource-aware slicing.	- Reduces carbon footprint. - Supports sustainable large-scale AI deployments.
High-Bandwidth	THz signal attenuation, blockage, and data demands (e.g., teleholograms, digital twins).	- AI-managed beamforming/channel estimation. - Reinforcement learning for adaptive resource allocation.	Enables ultra-HD applications (e.g., real-time sensor fusion, immersive AR/VR).
Scalability	- Scalability for 50B+ devices. - Privacy concerns in centralized systems.	- Federated Learning (FL) with edge nodes - AI middleware for workload orchestration - MARL for resource optimization	Supports IoT, smart cities, and privacy-sensitive AI (e.g., healthcare, industrial monitoring).
Security and Privacy	Vulnerabilities in distributed AI (e.g., adversarial attacks, data poisoning).	- AI-driven anomaly detection. - Homomorphic encryption and differential privacy - Decentralized trust frameworks.	- Protects sensitive data. - Ensures robust AI deployments in critical infrastructure.
Ethical and Regulatory Compliance	Bias, transparency, and accountability in autonomous AI decisions.	- Explainable AI (XAI) tools (e.g., SHAP). - Adaptive regulatory frameworks for AI governance.	- Builds public trust. - Ensures equitable resource allocation and compliance.

4.2. Resource-Efficiency

The growing use of large-scale AI workloads, especially GenAI and LLMs, introduces serious energy consumption issues that arise when deployed at scale [21]. For instance, an implementation of an advanced LLM, such as generative pre-trained transformer 4 (GPT-4) [22], can produce an energy footprint equivalent to the electricity consumption of about 100 average households spread over an entire year. This significant energy demand necessitates the integration of energy-aware design principles into 6G network architectures. As a solution to this shortcoming, 6G incorporates many neuromorphic computing paradigms, such as

spiking neural networks (SNNs) [23], which is a close emulation of biological neural networks that has displayed energy efficiency improvements as high as 4.6 x greater than classical AI-based systems [24]. The incorporation of hybrid energy harvesting methods, such as solar-powered network nodes, can further reduce energy waste while simultaneously processing workloads to match renewable energy sources and delay tolerances [25].

Algorithmic and system-level optimizations also enhance energy efficiency. Techniques such as model quantization, structured and unstructured pruning, and network architecture search reduce parameter redundancy and computational complexity, facilitating efficient workload processing in resource-constrained wireless environments [26]. Additionally, data-centric optimizations, such as selective sampling and prompt engineering, reduce unnecessary computations while maintaining model fidelity, significantly contributing to energy efficiency. Moreover, 6G incorporates energy-aware network slicing, enabling operators to allocate network resources like bandwidth and computational power based on real-time carbon intensity data [27]. Collectively, these approaches position 6G as a vital platform for sustainable and efficient AI deployments.

4.3. High-Bandwidth

6G networks are designed to operate in terahertz (THz) frequency bands (0.1–10 THz) and will permit transmission rates greater than 1 terabits per second (Tbps) [28, 29]. Such high rates enable demanding applications, including realistic and usable tele-holograms, real-time multi-sensor fusion for autonomous vehicles, and distributed AI model development. For instance, an autonomous vehicle employing lidar, radar, and 8K cameras can generate between 10 and 20 Tbps of raw data per hour [30]. Consequently, the continuous flow of raw sensor data must be efficiently transmitted to edge servers for immediate, safety-critical processing under stringent response-time requirements. Similarly, smart-city implementations involving digital twin networks represent another key scenario [31], where networks must constantly synchronize petabytes of urban sensor data, effectively pushing the performance limits of THz-based networks toward their theoretical maximum throughput. However, leveraging AI effectively at THz frequencies introduces significant technical challenges, as THz signals are highly susceptible to atmospheric absorption and environmental blockage. These issues will severely limit practical transmission distances to approximately 10 meters, substantially impacting effective network performance. To overcome these fundamental bandwidth limitations driven by AI-enabled applications, 6G networks must incorporate intelligent techniques designed and managed by AI:

- **Reconfigurable Beamforming:** dynamically adjusting antenna beams using AI algorithms to maintain stable high-bandwidth connections by proactively counteracting environmental blockages and signal attenuation.
- **Real-time Channel Estimation:** employing deep learning methods to rapidly model, predict, and respond to dynamic channel conditions at THz frequencies, thus ensuring uninterrupted and stable data delivery for AI-driven applications.
- **Adaptive Resource Allocation:** applying reinforcement learning to intelligently distribute spectrum resources according to real-time environmental conditions, application priorities, and user requirements, thereby optimizing bandwidth usage specifically for AI workloads.

By meeting these critical requirements through intelligent network management, AI transforms 6G bandwidth management from a traditionally static and rigid resource into a dynamically adaptive and flexible one, continuously optimized by AI in real-world deployments. Ultimately, this synergy between AI's network intelligence and THz-based communications empowers 6G networks to satisfy the demanding data requirements of advanced AI applications, delivering throughput beyond 1 Tbps while simultaneously adhering to strict latency and energy efficiency targets envisioned for next-generation wireless technologies.

4.4. Scalability

In order to successfully integrate artificial intelligence in future 6G networks, it is imperative to address some requirements that centralized cloud-based architectures supporting AI, cannot meet, especially with over 50 billion connected devices projected for 2030 [32]. Most experimental or in-use distributed AI architectures, in which processing is done at multiple edge nodes, are primarily designed for scalability and enhanced data privacy.

Distributed AI enables parallel processing across many edge nodes, which also increases network scalability by handling large device populations and a diversity of computing tasks. Scalability is critical for applications like autonomous vehicle coordination and industrial asset tracking, as well as immersive augmented reality (AR) experiences, all of which generate enormous amounts of data that necessitate local and distributed processing. Distributed AI architectures can also reduce privacy concerns associated with centralized data processing by employing Federated Learning (FL), in which edge devices are enabled to train machine learning models together on their local data without sending sensitive data outside the edge. This fully respects user privacy, provides faster response time, and reduces the burden on the network [33]. There are also hierarchical and hybrid FL based models which provide smarter aggregation of model updates from the edge together at intermediate nodes, further saving bandwidth and computation. Moreover, AI-driven middleware platforms within 6G networks are crucial in coordinating distributed AI tasks. These platforms seamlessly manage distributed training and inference operations across diverse hardware configurations, ensuring balanced computational workloads and operational efficiency. Autonomous AI and decentralized Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) further support these capabilities by enhancing resource allocation and facilitating dynamic network responsiveness. By focusing on scalability and privacy, distributed AI architectures enable 6G networks to effectively harness AI-driven innovations and support future technological advancements.

4.5. Security and Privacy

The extensive integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into 6G networks gives rise to important requirements relating to security and privacy due to the complexities and dynamic nature of large-scale distributed systems [34]. The AI-driven network architectures that are deployed at the network edge can become vulnerable to various types of security threats that include: adversarial attacks, model inversion attacks, and data poisoning attacks, due to their increased accessibility and distributed nature [35]. The protocols for security and privacy established by AI can evolve into sophisticated security solutions, such as anomaly detection, automated attack response, and adaptive trust management. AI-enabled systems can provide timely detection and mitigation of malicious cyber threats, and help increase the robustness

and resilience for networked AI applications. AI is also expanding the scope of privacy, as its implementation will necessitate the use of privacy-preserving frameworks. Collaborative AI methods will require alternative privacy-preserving techniques (e.g., differential privacy, secure multi-party computation, and homomorphic encryption) in which sensitive user data can be safeguarded when learning is decentralized. In summary, AI not only identifies important security and privacy issues, but also shapes and informs the framework under which security solutions and privacy-enhancing technologies are developed, ultimately ensuring trusted, secure, and robust 6G deployments.

4.6. Ethical and Regulatory Compliance

With the widespread use of AI for autonomous control of critical network functions in 6G, there are compelling ethical issues and regulatory compliance issues which need to be carefully addressed. AI-based decision-making will have a significant impact on essential network functions, such as resource allocation, management of access to the network, and priority of service decisions. As ethical issues of fairness, accountability, transparency, and non-discrimination come to bear on AI-based network decision-making, explainable AI (XAI) is crucial and valuable. XAI produces interpretable and transparent explanations for AI-based decisions, enabling auditing, promoting trust for users, and promoting accountability for network operators [36].

Moreover, the pervasive application of AI within 6G networks compels regulatory bodies to develop adaptive, continuously updated compliance frameworks. These frameworks must comprehensively address data privacy, security risks, and broader societal impacts resulting from AI integration. By explicitly embedding ethical considerations and regulatory compliance into AI systems and practices, 6G networks can ensure socially responsible and equitable technological advancement, fostering public trust and facilitating widespread adoption of future wireless technologies.

5. Summary

This white paper presented a quantitative overview of the intertwined requirements imposed by the co-evolution of AI and 6G, which are driven by the scenarios where AI enhances the design and operation of future networks, while 6G infrastructure must support the computational and operational demands of emerging AI paradigms. Through the emergence of essential use-cases, such as AI training and inference as a service, and LLM-based orchestration, we demonstrated how 6G must evolve into an AI-native platform for supporting dynamic resource allocation, intelligent data management, and programmable services, among others. On the other hand, we outlined how AI impacts 6G performance requirements over latency, bandwidth, energy efficiency, scalability, trust, to name a few. By measuring these mutual requirements, this paper offers a foundation for guiding standardization and system/network-level design, ensuring that future networks are not just optimized by AI, but they are AI-enabling platforms at their core.

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